

VARISTOR EFFECT WITH SMALL NONLINEARITY COEFFICIENT IN THE «METAL-TO-CARBON FILM» CONTACT JUNCTIONS

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A varistor effect is detected during measurements of the current-voltage characteristics (CVC) of “metal-to-carbon film” contact junctions. Carbon films in such samples were grown using magnetron sputtering of graphite in an inert atmosphere onto metal substrates. Since the films exhibit temperature behavior of resistance characteristic of semiconductor materials, the result was a metal-semiconductor contact junction. Electrical measurements demonstrate nonlinear symmetrical CVC-characteristics of the junctions, typical for the varistor effect with low classification voltages and a small nonlinearity coefficient.

Keywords: carbon films, metal-semiconductor contact junction, current-voltage characteristics, varistor effect.

Introduction. The formation of symmetrical nonlinear current-voltage characteristics in inhomogeneous semiconductor materials and composites is a promising task in modern electronic materials science. In turn, the use of modern composite materials to form electronic nonlinear elements (varistors), whose electrical conductivity depends on the applied voltage, is a pressing area of microelectronics development.

It should be noted, that the varistor effect (changing in the conductivity of single-crystal or polycrystalline semiconductor elements when exposed to an electric field) typically occurs at relatively high voltages (hundreds of volts). This may significantly limit the applicability of varistors in electronics for power generation applications (limiting only high voltages and surge breakdowns), while ignoring low-voltage micro- and nanoelectronics.

Therefore, the development of next-generation varistor devices based on modern nanocomposite materials (semiconductors, polymers, ceramics, etc.) is a highly promising area, both as the patterns determination of bipolar conductivity formation in such materials and the relationship between the main varistor characteristics and the parameters of the composite matrix used.

The so-called varistor effect (having properties similar to the operation of an array of series- and parallel-connected p-n junctions) is caused with the presence of a certain granular structure of the material. The size of granules, typically tens of micrometers in size, is crucial. The typical granule size directly influences the varistor's characteristics. It is well known that carbon (in particular, nanostructured carbon) has considerable potential for use in electronics [1], since under certain conditions it combines a dielectric, a conductor and a semiconductor, which makes the material unique. Therefore, the use of nanostructured carbon materials as a working substance can bring new possibilities to the development of new types of varistor devices with unique properties. In particular, it is possible to obtain cluster carbon structures with characteristic structural element sizes of hundreds (or even tens) of nanometers (rather than micrometers, as noted above) directly during the process of gas-phase film deposition. There are known works [2, 3] on the study of the varistor effect in thin polycrystalline diamond films, with a mosaic structure size not exceeding a few micrometers.

This paper presents the results of resistometric studies of “metal-to-carbon film” contact junctions, demonstrating the presence of symmetrical nonlinear current-voltage characteristics at voltages of several volts, typical for the varistor effect.

Experimental technique. Samples for the study were obtained by magnetron sputtering of graphite in an argon atmosphere (see also [4]). Carbon films were deposited on substrates of various metals (titanium, steel, etc.) and glass substrates. Plasma was generated using a planar DC magnetron with a flat cathode and an annular anode. Sample deposition conditions were as follows: chamber gas pressure of 150 mTorr, film growth time of 40 min, substrate temperature of 350°C, and magnetron current of 40 mA.

The primary method for studying the varistor effect is measuring the current-voltage characteristics. The electrical properties of the resulting samples were studied using the resistometric method under normal conditions. Conductivity and current-voltage characteristics were measured at the contact junction in the "metal substrate–carbon film–measuring contact" structure in the voltage range from -5 V to +5 V. On the film side, the brass pin contact with a rounding $R \sim 0.2$ mm was used. The temperature dependences of the resistance of carbon films deposited on glass substrates were also studied using the two-probe method in a heat chamber in the temperature range from room temperature to 150°C.

Main results and discussion. As previously demonstrated in [5, 6], a study of nucleation processes during the gas-phase growth of carbon films reveals a cluster-like nature of carbon deposition during magnetron sputtering. It is discovered that nanometer-sized carbon clusters, already formed in the plasma, are deposited on the substrate surface, from which certain nanostructures are formed.

The formation of such clusters in our case is caused with the relatively high buffer gas pressure [6] – approximately 150 mTorr. As a result, a relatively high density of sputtered atoms is observed within a small plasma zone. This leads to self-organization processes, namely, the formation of clusters from the target material in the magnetron plasma, being triggered even at a fairly moderate discharge temperature.

When the cluster flow hits a substrate that remains relatively cool compared to the plasma and cluster temperatures, they "freeze," simultaneously transferring thermal energy to the substrate. Figure 1 shows the globular/granular structure of the carbon film, with characteristic element (globule) sizes of tens to hundreds of nanometers. It is evident from the figure that small globules tend to aggregate into larger globular formations measuring ~ 250 nm.

Fig. 1. SEM image of the globular structure of the carbon film

As can be seen from fig. 2a, the temperature dependence of the resistance of the obtained carbon films has a classic semiconductor character: the resistance decreases with increasing temperature ($dR/dT < 0$). That is, the material has a negative temperature coefficient of resistance (TCR). It should be noted that a negative TCR is also typical for classical varistor structures. The temperature dependence of the resistance of the "metal-to-carbon film" contact junction also decreases monotonically with increasing temperature (see fig. 2b),

since the carbon film makes an overwhelming contribution to the resistance of the resulting junction, and the total TCR of the contact junction is negative too. For example, the TCR of the obtained titanium-carbon film contact is -0.0073 C^{-1} , and that of the steel-carbon film contact is -0.0064 C^{-1} . Thus, it is obvious that as a result of the experiment, metal-semiconductor contact junctions were obtained (where a carbon film is the semiconductor, with an estimated band gap of $\sim 0.2\text{-}0.3\text{ eV}$ [4]).

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of the resistance of the carbon film on a glass substrate (a) and the "titanium-carbon film" contact junction (b)

Figure 3 shows the current-voltage characteristics of the "steel-carbon film" and "titanium-carbon film" contacts under normal conditions. It is evident that the current-voltage characteristics have a symmetrical nonlinear dependence, typical for an ohmic contact (there is no potential barrier in the contact, or it is tunnel-transparent for electrons). It should be noted that a similar type of CVC is typical for samples of natural glassy carbon (shungite) from certain industrial deposits [7]. This shape of the curve indicates the presence of a varistor effect in the obtained samples at fairly low voltages. The estimated classification voltage (at the current of 1 mA through the sample) is $\sim 0.9\text{ V}$ for the "steel-carbon film" contact junction and $\sim 1.4\text{ V}$ (estimated by extrapolation) for the "titanium-carbon film" contact junction.

Fig. 3. Current-voltage characteristics of the "steel-carbon film" contact junction (a) and the "titanium-carbon film" contact junction (b)

An important parameter of varistors is the nonlinearity coefficient, defined as the ratio of static resistance to dynamic resistance for the same point of the current-voltage characteristic: $\lambda = R/R_d = U/I \cdot dI/dU$. The nonlinearity coefficient affects the varistor's operation, in particular, it determines the protective properties of the device during a sharp voltage increase. The nonlinearity coefficient λ can be determined by measuring the values of currents I_1 and I_2 , flowing through the varistor at two known voltage values U_1 and U_2 : $\lambda = \lg(I_2/I_1) / \lg(U_2/U_1)$. The nonlinearity coefficients λ of the current-voltage characteristics of the obtained “steel-carbon film” and “titanium-carbon film” contact junctions are relatively small compared to classical varistor materials (varying from 2 to 100) and are, respectively, 1.84 and 2.95.

Regarding the mechanism of the varistor effect occurrence in such structures, it is necessary to note the possible role of the tunneling effect. In the absence of direct contact between carbon particles (globules), but with sufficiently small interparticle gaps, electron tunneling occurs through such gaps. This leads to the formation of a comprehensive conductive structure in the film matrix (primarily in the form of chains of contacting particles), formed by aggregates of carbon globules. Presumably, the dominant conductivity mechanism at low currents is the intercalation of impurity atoms into the interlayer space of graphene planes in the carbon globule, while the contribution of nanoscale structural features to charge transfer is insignificant [7].

The estimated low characteristic values of the classification voltage can be explained with the relatively small size of carbon globules (fractions of a micrometer) and, accordingly, the relatively large initial number of conductive channels between these carbon globules. Further research is planned also with variations in the thickness of deposited carbon films to study the possibility of controlling the magnitude of the classification voltage and the permissible current through the “metal-carbon film” contact.

Conclusion. Nonlinear symmetrical sections of the current-voltage characteristics of the studied “metal-to-carbon film” contact junction samples are detected. Such CVCs are typical for the varistor effect, with an estimated classification voltage of 1-2 V and small nonlinearity coefficient. Probably, the varistor effect is due to the globular structure of carbon films, where electrical conductivity is determined with conductive channels between carbon clusters/globules. At low voltages, the number of conductive channels is relatively small, and the conductivity dependence is ohmic. As the voltage increases, the probability of charge carrier tunneling between clusters increases, thereby increasing the number of conductivity channels and achieving a nonlinear conductivity dependence for the sample. Presumably, the proposed materials can be used as a working substance for the development and optimization of low-voltage varistors and other carbon-based electronic devices.

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**ВАРИСТОРНЫЙ ЭФФЕКТ С МАЛЫМ КОЭФФИЦИЕНТОМ НЕЛИНЕЙНОСТИ В
КОНТАКТНЫХ ПЕРЕХОДАХ “МЕТАЛЛ-УГЛЕРОДНАЯ ПЛЕНКА”**

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Обнаружен варисторный эффект при измерении вольт-амперных характеристик (ВАХ) контактных переходов «металл-углеродная плёнка», в которых пленки выращивались методом магнетронного распыления графита в инертной атмосфере на металлические подложки. Поскольку температурное поведение сопротивления пленок характерно для полупроводниковых материалов, в результате получен контактный переход металл–полупроводник. Электрические измерения демонстрируют нелинейные симметричные ВАХ переходов, характерные для варисторного эффекта с невысокими значениями классификационного напряжения и малым коэффициентом нелинейности.

Ключевые слова: углеродные пленки, контакт металл-полупроводник, вольт-амперные характеристики, варисторный эффект.

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